

ACCEPTABILITY AND MARKETABILITY OF GUOKCA ICE CREAM

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Acceptability and Marketability of GUOKCA Ice Cream

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the level of acceptability and marketability of GUOKCA (Guyabano, Okra, Camote Tops) ice cream of selected students and faculty of Francisco P. Felix Memorial National High School during the School Year 2023-2024. experimental method of research was used, utilizing survey questionnaire as the data gathering instrument. This study also used the 9 - point Hedonic rating scale for the acceptability and 5-point Likert scale for the marketability of the GUOKCA Ice Cream. There were thirty (30) Teenagers, thirty (30) Young Adults, and thirty (30) Adult respondents which included students and faculty members evaluated the acceptability and marketability of this research. The data revealed that the three groups of respondents, namely teenagers, young adults, and adult respondents evaluated the appearance, aroma, taste and texture of GUOKCA Ice Cream with 45ml, 90ml, and 120ml proportions as Very Acceptable. In addition, there were no significant differences on the evaluation of the three groups of respondents on the level of acceptability of GUOKCA Ice Cream. On the other hand, the level of marketability as evaluated by respondents obtained a rating of Very High Potential utilizing the 45ml, 90ml, and 120ml proportions in terms of supply availability, production cost, and consumer demand resulting to no significant difference on their evaluations. Furthermore, the results of physicochemical analysis from the produced GUOKCA ice cream contains 7.08 for sugar, 68.7 moisture, and less than 3* for Vitamins C with a pH Level of 5.01 at 23.5°C. Comments and suggestions were given by the three groups of respondents for further improvement of the product.

Keywords: *acceptability, marketability, physicochemical analysis, ice cream*

Introduction

Philippines is known to have a humid temperature and a hot climate, compare to other countries, that have different seasons. In the Philippines, there is only summer and rainy days. Moreover, The Philippines' hottest months are April and May, with the coldest months experienced during December, January and February. Due to different seasons, and the hotness temperature, ice cream became popular in the Philippines.

According to Monsel (2020), ice cream is a mixture of milk, cream, sugar, and sometimes other ingredients that has been frozen into a soft, creamy delight using special techniques. Ice cream has been a popular treat for hundreds of years but has only become commonplace since the widespread use of refrigeration. The exploding popularity of ice cream has led to a few ice-cream variations including frozen custard, frozen yogurt, and even non-dairy versions made with ingredients like coconut milk.

The first ice cream that is very popular in the country is sorbetes. This is supported by Atlas (2022) who said that sorbetes is a popular Filipino ice cream flavored with ingredients such as mango, chocolate, cheese, coconut, and purple yam (ube). Traditionally, it is produced from carabao's milk and served in tiny scoops on sugar cones.

The increasing demand for ice creams and growing inclination toward impulse ice cream desserts fuel the growth of the global ice cream ingredients market. On the other hand, rising prevalence of lactose intolerance and surge in diabetic population impede the growth to some extent. However, the introduction of novel combinations & low-fat/sugar ingredients and rise in craze for organic food products are expected to create lucrative opportunities in the industry (Allied Market Research, 2022).

The Guyabano, with its green, slightly spiky skin encases a white, creamy pulp abundant in a variety of nutrients. To obtain these highly nutritious and flavorful fruits, visit your local fresh food markets or stores. The medicinal potential of the guyabano fruit can be used to treat anything from poor liver function to skin conditions. Its medicinal properties can be accredited to its list of nutrients. The flesh of this exotic fruit holds high quantities of vitamin C, fiber, calcium, phosphorus and potassium. Furthermore, Guyabano contains beneficial acids that work together with vitamins to support numerous bodily processes.

Okra also known as gumbo or ladies' fingers, is a warm-season vegetable. It is a good source of minerals, vitamins, antioxidants, and fiber. It contains a sticky juice that people use to thicken sauces.

Camote tops, sweet potato leaves are nothing else, but a plant fused together with all the nutrients you could ever expect for thin flat green blades to have. In fact, it boasts itself through containing significant amounts of fibers and other micronutrients such as potassium, beta-carotene, lutein, xanthine, vitamins such as B6, C and D iron, and magnesium. Some health benefits of camote tops are prevent eye degeneration, protection to heart disease and stroke, strengthen body tissues, promote healthy digestive tract, regulates blood circulation, natural pain killer and versatile health ally.

Due to the growing demands of ice cream, that results to the increase of people that were diagnosed with diabetes, it is important to invent or create ingredients that are healthy, and will allow people to enjoy ice cream, with a healthy benefit. This may be done through adding ingredients that are very nutritious like: guyabano, okra, and camote tops extract that known for rich in fiber, antioxidant and

vitamins. Considering the necessity to consume healthier food selection is more of a need than a want for a good health and wellbeing. With this in mind as a food technology student, the researcher came up with the idea of incorporating blended guyabano fruit, okra fruit, and camote tops extract, as Ice Cream ingredients with the use of Stevia powdered sugar as an ice cream sweetener. Consumers believe that it is a must to consider the aroma, taste and texture of the ice cream, as well as its nutritional benefits, among the consumers.

Research Questions

The study which aimed to determine the level of acceptability and marketability of GUOKCA (Guyabano, Okra, Camote Tops) ice cream was conducted at Francisco P. Felix Memorial National High School during S.Y 2023-2024. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the evaluation of the three groups of respondents on the level of acceptability of GUOKCA ice cream with 45ml, 90ml, and 120ml proportions in terms of the following criteria?
 - 1.1. appearance;
 - 1.2. aroma;
 - 1.3. taste; and
 - 1.4. texture?
2. Are there significant differences among the evaluations of the three groups of respondents on the level of acceptability of GUOKCA ice cream with 45ml, 90ml, and 120ml proportions in terms of the above cited criteria?
3. What is the evaluation of the three groups of respondents on the level of marketability of GUOKCA ice cream with 45ml, 90ml, and 120ml proportions in terms of the following aspects?
 - 3.1. supply availability;
 - 3.2. production cost; and
 - 3.3. consumer demand?
4. Are there significant differences among the evaluation of three groups of respondents on the level of marketability of GUOKCA ice cream with 45ml, 90ml and 12ml proportions in terms of above-mentioned aspects?
5. What is the physicochemical analysis of GUOKCA ice cream in terms of the following?
 - 5.1. sugar;
 - 5.2. vitamins c;
 - 5.3. pH level; and
 - 5.4. moisture?
6. What comments and suggestions are given by the respondents to further improve the marketability and acceptability of GUOKCA ice cream?

Literature Review

According to Colorado Integrated Food Safety Center of Excellence (2022), Ice cream is a common dessert product that is produced through the pasteurization and homogenization of blended dairy products, (typically milk, condensed milk, butterfat, and cream). Other ingredients such as sweetening agents, flavorings, stabilizers, emulsifiers, colorings are also added to the mix. Occasionally, fruits, nuts, variegates, candy pieces, and other condiments are added to make a desired ice cream flavor. The process then involves freezing the mixture and incorporating air.

In addition, Corradini (2019) added that color plays an essential role in food appearance and acceptability. Synthetic or artificial colors, i.e., coloring agents that are not nature-identical and have been obtained by chemical synthesis, are routinely added to food products to impart desirable sensory characteristics. The food industry has historically favored synthetic color additives over natural colorants due to their comparatively low cost, high coloring ability, and stability to processing and storage conditions. Although consumer preferences towards clean labels and health concerns associated with the use of synthetic dyes are reverting this practice, approved synthetic colors are still widespread in the food supply.

Moreover, Corriher (2022), added that one of the joys of making ice cream at home is having the freedom to change ingredients and personalize a recipe to suit my mood. When an ice-cream mixture gets poured into a machine and stirred, some of the liquid freezes into pure ice crystals while some of it remains liquid. The goal is to keep these developing ice crystals small and plentiful, and make it a smooth, creamy texture.

Mark (2021) mentioned in an article the reason why ice cream smell matters. According to experts, smell is an important part of enjoying food and plays an important role in how we experience the treat because it makes a person feel excited to taste the food. In other words, the food aroma plays an important part in enjoying food because it activates one's desire and excitement.

Esteron (2023) conducted a study entitled, "Acceptability and Marketability of Tomato, Carrot and Moth Beans as Flavors of Ice Cream". The findings of the study showed that the three groups of respondents, namely Food Experts, Sellers, and Consumer had different evaluation as regards the level of acceptability of the 25g and 75g proportion, while the 50g proportion was evaluated as Very Acceptable by the three groups. In addition, the respondents evaluated the level of marketability of the product as to Consumer Demand,

Production Cost and Supply Availability as More Preferred.

Brennan (2020) explained that Okra or sometimes called “lady’s finger,” okra is a flowering plant with edible seed pods. It grows best in warm climates and is often cultivated in Africa and South Asia. Though technically a fruit, okra often gets used like a vegetable in cooking. You might be familiar with okra as an ingredient in gumbo, for example. Though not necessarily a household name in healthy foods, okra still has plenty of nutritional value. Okra is low in calories but packed full of nutrients. The vitamin C in okra helps support healthy immune function. Okra is also rich in vitamin K, which helps your body clot blood.

Methodology

Research Design

The researcher utilized the experimental method of research to achieve its goal which is to resolve the acceptability and marketability of GUOKCA as ice cream ingredients with 45ml, 90ml and 120ml of guyabano, okra and camote tops extract.

According to Leppink (2019), an experiment is a research method designed to prove the cause-and-effect relationships among actions, applications, or techniques while investigating a variety of factors that react with the actions, applications, or techniques.

Participants

The sources of data of this study, as shown in Table 1, were the 30 teenagers, ages 13-19 years old, 30 young adults, ages 20-29 years old, and 30 adults, ages 30 years old and above, of selected students and faculty of Francisco P. Felix Memorial National High School, Cainta, Rizal during the School Year 2023-2024.

Instruments

A survey questionnaire was done to assess the acceptability and marketability of ice cream with blended guyabano, okra fruit and camote tops extract in 45ml, 90ml and 120ml.

Procedure

To reach the study's objectives, the researcher followed certain steps. The researcher collected the necessary information using the procedure outlined below. First, the researcher made enough amount of GUOKCA Ice Cream for the survey. Second, the questionnaire was designed and delivered to her research adviser for clearance. The questionnaire includes thirty-one (31) indicators connected to the target respondents' evaluation of the ice cream. The questionnaire employed a nine-point Hedonic Scale and a five-point Likert Scale to assess respondents' opinions on each statement. The researcher sought many professionals to validate the survey questionnaire/checklist. After the process of validation, the questionnaire was improved through the guidance of the thesis adviser. Next, communication letters were prepared and sent to the people that are involved in the research process. Then, developed food product samples will be sent or laboratory testing. After which, the researcher made ninety copies, which were distributed to thirty (30) Teenagers, thirty (30) Young Adults, and thirty (30) Adults from Francisco P. Felix Memorial National High School.

The researcher personally collected the questionnaires filled by the three types of respondents. The records and data gathered from validators and respondents were maintained under strict confidentiality measures. The report and interpretation did not include or display any individual names. Following data gathering, the researcher evaluated the pertinent information for the research piece.

Ethical Considerations

In this research, ethical considerations were carefully considered. Participants were asked for their informed consent before joining the study, and they were assured that they could withdraw at any time without consequences. All information provided by participants was treated confidentially, and their identities were replaced with codes to maintain anonymity. Measures were implemented to ensure the well-being and safety of participants throughout the study. The research protocol was reviewed and approved by the ethics committee to ensure its compliance with ethical standards. Additionally, the research was conducted with respect for cultural differences, and the data collected were used honestly and accurately in the analysis and reporting.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the findings according to the study's research questions.

Evaluation of the Three Groups of Respondents (Teenager, Years Old, Young Adults 20-29 Years Old and Adults 30 Years and Above) on the Level of Acceptability of GUOKCA Ice Cream with 45ml, 90ml, and 120ml Proportions

For 45mL Proportion

It can be gleaned in the table that in terms of appearance, the respondents evaluated the GUOKCA ice cream with 45 mL Proportion as Very Acceptable as evidenced by the weighted means of 7.86, 8.42, and 8.10. This signifies that the color of the ice cream is not close to its base ingredient means too pale or too vivid that marked effect on the acceptability of the ice cream. As supported in the study of Panso (2021), the result is similar because both studies gained the same rating from respondents as Very Acceptable (VA).

This implies that evaluators from both studies believe that appearance influences consumer perception.

Table 1. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of GUOKCA Ice Cream with 45 mL Proportion as regards Appearance

Indicators	Respondents					
	Teenagers		Young Adults		Adults	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Looks delicate and Appetizing.	7.40	MA	8.17	VA	8.00	VA
2. The color is pleasing and indicative of the flavor.	7.90	VA	8.53	EA	8.03	VA
3. No sign of residue.	7.87	VA	8.33	VA	8.07	VA
4. The packaging is presentable.	8.27	VA	8.63	EA	8.30	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	7.86	VA	8.42	VA	8.10	VA

Note: WM – Weighted Mean VI – Verbal Interpretation VA – Very Acceptable

Table 2. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of GUOKCA Ice Cream with 45 mL Proportion as regards Aroma

Indicators	Respondents					
	Teenagers		Young Adults		Adults	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The ice cream has a natural smell of guyabano fruit, okra fruit and camote tops extract.	8.07	VA	8.30	VA	8.10	VA
2. It has a pleasant aroma.	7.87	VA	8.20	VA	8.33	VA
3. It has desirable smell.	7.53	VA	8.30	VA	8.30	VA
4. The smell is associated with the flavor.	8.20	VA	8.40	VA	8.30	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	7.92	VA	8.30	VA	8.26	VA

The table shows that the teenagers, young adults, and adult respondents rated the aroma as Very Acceptable with an overall weighted mean of 7.92, 8.30, and 8.26 respectively. This implies that the GUOKCA ice cream with 45ml proportion as regards to aroma has desirable smell more than just how it tastes. In the study of Jandayan (2020), It is recommended to consider the taste, texture, aroma, appearance, and its nutritional benefits in making ice cream to attain acceptability from the costumer's point of view.

Table 3. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of GUOKCA Ice Cream with 45 mL Proportion as regards Taste

Indicators	Respondents					
	Teenagers		Young Adults		Adults	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Taste good and appealing.	8.20	VA	8.33	VA	8.00	VA
2. It tastes natural/pure.	8.33	VA	8.50	EA	8.40	VA
3. It has a well-blended flavor.	8.33	VA	8.53	EA	8.23	VA
4. It has no after taste.	8.03	VA	8.23	VA	8.20	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.23	VA	8.40	VA	8.21	VA

The table reveals that the respondents evaluated the GUOKCA ice cream with 45ml proportion as regards to taste as Very Acceptable (VA) with weighted means of 8.23, 8.40, and 8.21. This finding implies the respondents strongly believe that a well-blended flavor enhances the taste of ice cream. It contains the exact amount of ingredients to taste. The result of this study is somewhat similar to the findings in the study of Esteron (2023) since taste is one of the criteria used. The result showed that the prepared ice cream with different proportions gained the same rating from all evaluators which means it is acceptable among the three groups of respondents.

Table 4. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of GUOKCA Ice Cream with 45 mL Proportion as regards Texture

Indicators	Respondents					
	Teenagers		Young Adults		Adults	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. It has fine and smooth texture.	8.27	VA	8.00	VA	8.30	VA
2. Serving temperature affects product quality.	7.93	VA	8.37	VA	8.03	VA
3. Melt pleasantly and not too quickly in the mouth.	8.00	VA	8.33	VA	8.37	VA
4. It is appealing to the mouth.	8.27	VA	8.23	VA	8.37	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.12	VA	8.23	VA	8.27	VA

As seen in the table, the teenagers, young adults, and adult respondents rated GUOKCA ice cream with 45ml proportion as regards to texture as Very Acceptable (VA) with the overall weighted means of 8.12,8.23, and 8.27 respectively. This implies that the respondents agreed that the ice cream ingredients complement each other. As Corriher (2022) stated that to attain suitability of ice cream taste, appropriate measure should be done. When an ice-cream mixture gets poured into a machine and stirred, some of the liquid freezes

into pure ice crystals while some of it remains liquid. The goal is to keep these developing ice crystals small and plentiful to attain smooth and creamy texture.

For 90ml Proportion

Table 5. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of GUOKCA Ice Cream with 90 ml Proportion as regards Appearance

Indicators	Respondents					
	Teenagers		Young Adults		Adults	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Looks delicate and Appetizing.	8.40	VA	8.57	EA	8.53	EA
2. The color is pleasing and indicative of the flavor.	8.50	EA	8.57	EA	8.43	VA
3. No sign of residue.	8.50	EA	8.50	EA	8.47	VA
4. The packaging is presentable.	8.57	EA	8.77	EA	8.60	EA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.49	VA	8.60	EA	8.51	EA

According to the table, teenager respondents rated the GUOKCA ice cream with 90mL proportion as Very Acceptable (VA) with an overall weighted mean of 8.49, while young adults and adult respondents rated the GUOKCA ice cream with 90mL proportion as Extremely Acceptable (EA) with an overall weighted mean of 8.60 for young adults and 8.51 for adult respondents, respectively. The data showed that the appearance of the product, it may be the color and shape of the ice cream or the packaging, attracts the respondents' interest maybe because the ice cream has unique and tempting appearance that arouses curiosity to taste the product. This supports the study of Corradini (2019) that color plays an essential role in food appearance and acceptability for it impacts one's desirable sensory. Its pleasant, delicate, and appetizing appeal fascinates consumers.

Table 6. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of GUOKCA Ice Cream with 90 ml Proportion as regards Aroma

Indicators	Respondents					
	Teenagers		Young Adults		Adults	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The ice cream has a natural smell of guyabano fruit, okra fruit and camote tops extract.	8.57	EA	8.60	EA	8.30	VA
2. It has a pleasant aroma.	8.27	VA	8.43	VA	8.47	VA
3. It has desirable smell.	8.03	VA	8.50	EA	8.30	VA
4. The smell is associated with the flavor.	8.43	VA	8.63	EA	8.43	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.33	VA	8.54	EA	8.38	VA

The table shows that teenagers and adult respondents have the same evaluation on the acceptance of GUOKCA ice cream with 90 ml proportion in terms of aroma, as evidenced by the overall weighted mean of 8.33 for teenagers and 8.38 for adults, all interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA), while young adult respondents rated the aroma with an overall weighted mean of 8.54, interpreted as Extremely Acceptable (EA). This indicates that the ice cream smell though pleases the respondents' liking it does not influence the expected perceived taste. This supports what Gopal (2023) mentioned that to enjoy food like ice cream, it involves senses. Smell is one of the senses. Food like ice cream should have a natural and pleasant aroma to captivate liking.

Table 7. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of GUOKCA Ice Cream with 90 ml Proportion as regards Taste

Indicators	Respondents					
	Teenagers		Young Adults		Adults	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Taste good and appealing.	8.60	EA	8.43	VA	8.23	VA
2. It tastes natural/pure.	8.57	EA	8.63	EA	8.43	VA
3. It has a well-blended flavor.	8.53	EA	8.53	EA	8.17	VA
4. It has no after taste.	8.50	EA	8.20	VA	8.13	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.55	EA	8.45	VA	8.24	VA

As seen on Table 10, the teenagers, young adults, and adult respondents' evaluation varied from each other as evident from its overall weighted mean of 8.55, interpreted as Extremely Acceptable (EA), 8.45, interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA) and 8.24, interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA), respectively. The data also showed that the ice cream contains an original flavor the suits the taste of the respondents. Sipple, et al. (2022) concluded that ice cream products are preferred both conceptually and with regard to taste.

It can be gleaned in the table that the teenagers and adult respondents rated GUOKCA Ice Cream with 90ml proportion as regards to texture as Very Acceptable (VA) with an overall weighted mean of 8.40 and 8.38, while young adult respondents with an overall weighted mean of 8.55. These results imply that during its manufacturing, regarding its desirable taste, mouth feel, flavor, body and

texture many aspects should be considered to meet customers' demands. As supported in the study of Srinu and Dorai (2022) that flavor and taste have a commercial opportunity especially with health advantages.

Table 8. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of GUOKCA Ice Cream with 90 ml Proportion as regards Texture

Indicators	Respondents					
	Teenagers		Young Adults		Adults	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. It has fine and smooth texture.	8.50	EA	8.50	EA	8.30	VA
2. Serving temperature affects product quality.	8.23	VA	8.57	EA	8.33	VA
3. Melt pleasantly and not too quickly.	8.40	VA	8.57	EA	8.47	VA
4. It is appealing to the mouth.	8.47	VA	8.57	EA	8.43	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.40	VA	8.55	EA	8.38	VA

For 120ml Proportion

Based on the table 12, the teenagers, young adults, and adult respondents rated the appearance with an overall weighted mean of 8.31, interpreted as Very Acceptable (VA), 8.62 interpreted as Extremely Acceptable (EA) and 8.56 interpreted as Extremely Acceptable (EA), respectively. The results imply that the ice cream is visually appealing to the respondents that influences acceptability of the product as regards to appearance. This supports what Kot et al., (2021) concluded that to obtain more stable products, the most potential application to consider is the satisfying physical appearance of ice cream for this contributed the most for product sustainability.

Table 9. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of GUOKCA Ice Cream with 120 ml Proportion as regards Appearance

Indicators	Respondents					
	Teenagers		Young Adults		Adults	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Looks delicate and Appetizing.	8.37	VA	8.63	EA	8.60	EA
2. The color is pleasing and indicative of the flavor.	8.27	VA	8.60	EA	8.50	EA
3. No sign of residue.	8.30	VA	8.53	EA	8.47	VA
4. The packaging is presentable.	8.30	VA	8.70	EA	8.67	EA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.31	VA	8.62	EA	8.56	EA

Table 10. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of GUOKCA Ice Cream with 120 ml Proportion as regards Aroma

Indicators	Respondents					
	Teenagers		Young Adults		Adults	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The ice cream has a natural smell of guyabano fruit, okra and camote tops extract.	8.53	EA	8.60	EA	8.53	EA
2. It has a pleasant aroma.	8.40	VA	8.43	VA	8.53	EA
3. It has desirable smell.	8.03	VA	8.47	VA	8.43	VA
4. The smell is associated with the flavor.	8.27	VA	8.57	EA	8.50	EA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.31	VA	8.52	EA	8.50	EA

It can be gleaned in the table that the teenager respondents rated GUOKCA ice cream with 120ml proportion as regards to aroma as Very Acceptable, while young adults and adult respondents rated GUOKCA ice cream with 120ml proportion as regards to aroma as Extremely Acceptable as evident in an overall weighted mean of 8.31,8.52, and 8.50, respectively. It also showed that the three group of respondents positively appreciated that the product has a natural smell of guyabano fruit, okra fruit, and camote tops extract. As supported in the study of Concepcion (2023) in which the three groups of respondents showed positive results on the aroma of the product because of its balanced natural smell.

Table 11. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of GUOKCA Ice Cream with 120 ml Proportion as regards Taste

Indicators	Respondents					
	Teenagers		Young Adults		Adults	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Taste good and appealing.	8.63	EA	8.60	EA	8.47	VA
2. It tastes natural/pure.	8.63	EA	8.57	EA	8.57	EA
3. It has a well-blended flavor.	8.50	EA	8.50	EA	8.37	VA
4. It has no after taste.	8.57	EA	7.57	VA	8.43	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.58	EA	8.31	VA	8.46	VA

As shown in Table 11 that the teenager respondents rated GUOKCA ice cream with 120ml proportion as regards to taste as Extremely Acceptable, while young adults and adult as Very acceptable as evident in an overall weighted mean of 8.58, 8.31, and 8.46, respectively. This may show that for the respondents, the ice cream has a slightly satisfying taste that results in a slightly appreciated taste. Sipple et al. (2022) concluded from the consumers perception that the most important factor for purchase of ice cream product is its indulgence flavor or taste for these impacts' costumers' preference with regards to taste.

Table 12. Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of GUOKCA Ice Cream with 120 ml Proportion as regards Texture

Indicators	Respondents					
	Teenagers		Young Adults		Adults	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. It has fine and smooth texture.	8.47	VA	8.40	VA	8.53	EA
2. Serving temperature affects product quality.	8.40	VA	8.33	VA	8.50	EA
3. Melt pleasantly and not too quickly in the mouth.	8.40	VA	8.50	EA	8.50	EA
4. It is appealing to the mouth.	8.37	VA	8.47	VA	8.40	VA
Overall Weighted Mean	8.41	VA	8.43	VA	8.48	VA

The table revealed that teenagers, young adults, and adult respondents rated GUOKCA ice cream with 120ml proportion as regards to texture as Very Acceptable as evidenced by the overall weighted means of 8.41, 8.43, and 8.48, respectively. accepted in the four indicators by the three groups of respondents as to texture. This supported what Williams (2021) stated that texture plays a strong role in the entire eating experience for it is vital in food and drink formulation for consumer acceptance or instant aversion because texture's impact is not only limited to mouthfeel but heightens sensory experience and often contributes a greater feeling of indulgence.

Significant Differences Among the Evaluations of the Three Groups of Respondents on the Level of Acceptability of GUOKCA Ice Cream with Three Different Proportions

Table 13. Summary of Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of GUOKCA Ice Cream with 45 ml Proportions

Criteria	Computed F Value	Critical F Value	Decision	Interpretation
a. Appearance	2.93	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
b. Aroma	1.39	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
c. Taste	0.47	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
d. Texture	0.24	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant

These results showed that GUOKCA ice cream with 45 ml proportion had appetizing and attractive color appearance, mouthwatering and balanced natural smell aroma, pleasurable and consistent texture, and flavorsome and delightful taste which results positive impact from all groups of respondents.

Table 14. Summary of Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of GUOKCA Ice Cream with 90 ml Proportions

Criteria	Computed F Value	Critical F Value	Decision	Interpretation
a. Appearance	0.36	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
b. Aroma	0.66	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
c. Taste	1.42	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
d. Texture	0.49	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant

These results explained that GUOKCA ice cream with 90 ml proportion had pleasing and presentable appearance, had natural aroma of guyabano fruit, okra fruit, and camote tops extract, well-blended flavor, and taste good, has fine and smooth texture that captivate respondents' interest of the product.

Table 15. Summary of Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Evaluations on the Acceptability Level of GUOKCA Ice Cream with 120 ml Proportions

Criteria	Computed F Value	Critical F Value	Decision	Interpretation
a. Appearance	1.28	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
b. Aroma	0.48	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
c. Taste	0.93	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant
d. Texture	0.08	3.10	Fail to Reject the H ₀	Not Significant

According to the data, GUOKCA as ice cream ingredients with 120 mL proportion had unique appearance and no sign of residue, aroma was associated with the flavor, acceptable texture, and satisfying and palatable taste that pleased respondents' satisfaction.

Evaluation of the Three Groups of Respondents on the Level of Marketability of GUOKCA Ice Cream with Different Proportions

For 45 ml Proportion

Table 16. Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of GUOKCA Ice Cream with 45 ml Proportion of Supply Availability

Indicators	Respondents					
	Teenagers		Young Adults		Adults	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Guyabano, Okra and Camote tops are available all year round.	4.87	VHP	4.53	VHP	4.60	VHP
2. The materials could be produced easily.	4.80	VHP	4.70	VHP	4.67	VHP
3. Snacks like ice cream need less effort to produce.	4.87	VHP	4.47	HP	4.63	VHP
4. The Ingredients cost less.	4.87	VHP	4.67	VHP	4.63	VHP
5. The raw materials for the product are locally available.	4.93	VHP	4.80	VHP	4.87	VHP
Overall Weighted Mean	4.87	VHP	4.63	VHP	4.68	VHP

It can be observed on Table 26 that the teenagers, young adults, and adult respondents evaluated the supply availability as Very High Potential with overall weighted means of 4.87, 4.63, and 4.68, respectively. This may mean that pertaining with supply availability of guyabano fruit, okra, and camote tops will not be a problem because the ingredients are available all year round. The fruits generally grow in locations where the crop will receive full sunlight throughout the day.

Table 17. Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of GUOKCA Ice Cream with 45 ml Proportion of Production Cost

Indicators	Respondents					
	Teenagers		Young Adults		Adults	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. It has a competitive price.	4.90	VHP	4.60	VHP	4.73	VHP
2. It is economical.	4.90	VHP	4.60	VHP	4.83	VHP
3. It is cheaper due to the abundance of localized material.	4.90	VHP	4.60	VHP	4.80	VHP
4. Little manpower is needed in making ice cream.	4.97	VHP	4.60	VHP	4.90	VHP
5. It needs little capital to produce the product.	4.80	VHP	4.67	VHP	4.87	VHP
Overall Weighted Mean	4.89	VHP	4.61	VHP	4.83	VHP

It is presented on the table that the teenagers, young adults, and adult respondents evaluated the supply availability as Very High Potential with the overall weighted means of 4.89, 4.61, and 4.83, respectively. This indicates that, pertaining with price, it is economical and cheap due to the abundance of localized material.

Table 18. Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of GUOKCA Ice Cream with 45 ml Proportion of Consumer Demand

Indicators	Respondents					
	Teenagers		Young Adults		Adults	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The product can meet the consumer demand.	5.00	VHP	4.73	VHP	4.73	VHP
2. It can satisfy the consumer because of its nutritive value.	5.00	VHP	4.67	VHP	4.80	VHP
3. It could be sold at lower price compared to other commercially prepared ice creams.	5.00	VHP	4.77	VHP	4.77	VHP
4. It could be likened by people all ages.	5.00	VHP	4.70	VHP	4.63	VHP
5. Guyabano fruit, Okra fruit and camote tops extract have health benefits.	5.00	VHP	4.90	VHP	4.80	VHP
Overall Weighted Mean	5.00	VHP	4.75	VHP	4.75	VHP

It is perceptible on the table that the teenagers, young adults, and adult respondents evaluated the consumer demand as Very High Potential with the overall weighted means of 5.00, 4.75, and 4.75, respectively. This could mean that the product can be sold easily once it is offered in the market because the product can meet the consumer demand, will be liked by all types of ages, and it has nutritional benefits.

For 90 ml Proportion

As presented on the table, the teenagers, young adults, and adult respondents evaluated the supply availability as Very High Potential

with the overall weighted means of 4.88, 4.71, and 4.73, respectively. This implies that guyabano, okra and camote tops are widely available because it is locally produced, and ingredients cost affordable price that customers can meet.

Table 19. Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of GUOKCA Ice Cream with 90 ml Proportion of Supply Availability

Indicators	Respondents					
	Teenagers		Young Adults		Adults	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Guyabano, Okra and Camote tops are available all year round.	4.87	VHP	4.63	VHP	4.70	VHP
2. The materials could be produced easily.	4.83	VHP	4.83	VHP	4.80	VHP
3. Snacks like ice cream need less effort to produce.	4.87	VHP	4.47	HP	4.60	VHP
4. The Ingredients cost less.	4.90	VHP	4.70	VHP	4.67	VHP
5. The raw materials for the product are locally available.	4.93	VHP	4.93	VHP	4.87	VHP
Overall Weighted Mean	4.88	VHP	4.71	VHP	4.73	VHP

Table 20. Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of GUOKCA Ice Cream with 90 ml Proportion of Production Cost

Indicators	Respondents					
	Teenagers		Young Adults		Adults	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. It has a competitive price.	4.90	VHP	4.63	VHP	4.73	VHP
2. It is economical.	4.93	VHP	4.67	VHP	4.83	VHP
3. It is cheaper due to the abundance of localized material.	4.93	VHP	4.73	VHP	4.80	VHP
4. Little manpower is needed in making ice cream.	4.97	VHP	4.50	VHP	4.90	VHP
5. It needs little capital to produce the product.	4.97	VHP	4.73	VHP	4.87	VHP
Overall Weighted Mean	4.94	VHP	4.65	VHP	4.83	VHP

Based on the table, the teenager, young adults, and adult respondents evaluated the production cost as Very High Potential with the overall weighted means of 4.94, 4.65, 4.83, respectively. This could mean that in making ice cream using guyabano, okra, and camote tops as ingredients need a little capital to produce the product because ingredients are affordable and readily available in the market.

Table 21. Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of GUOKCA Ice Cream with 90 ml Proportion of Consumer Demand

Indicators	Respondents					
	Teenagers		Young Adults		Adults	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The product can meet the consumer demand.	4.97	VHP	4.87	VHP	4.73	VHP
2. It can satisfy the consumer because of its nutritive value.	4.97	VHP	4.73	VHP	4.83	VHP
3. It could be sold at lower price compared to other commercially prepared ice creams.	4.97	VHP	4.70	VHP	4.77	VHP
4. It could be likened by people all ages.	4.97	VHP	4.67	VHP	4.63	VHP
5. Guyabano fruit, Okra fruit and camote tops extract have health benefits.	4.97	VHP	4.83	VHP	4.83	VHP
Overall Weighted Mean	4.97	VHP	4.76	VHP	4.76	VHP

The table shows that the teenagers, young adults, and adult respondents evaluated the consumer demand of GUOKCA Ice Cream with 90ml proportion as Very High Potential with the overall weighted means of 4.97, 4.76, and 4.76, respectively. This finding implies that the product can meet the demand of the consumers and can satisfy the consumer because of its nutritive value.

For 120 ml Proportion

It can be viewed on the table that the teenagers, young adults, and adult respondents evaluated the supply availability of GUOKCA ice cream with 120ml proportion as Very High Potential with the overall weighted means of 4.91, 4.62, and 4.70, respectively. The data imply that GUOKCA ice cream with 120ml proportion with respect to supply availability will not be a problem because snacks like ice cream need less effort to produce. The process is easy to follow, and ingredients are widely available.

Table 22. Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of GUOKCA Ice Cream with 120 ml Proportion of Supply Availability

Indicators	Respondents					
	Teenagers		Young Adults		Adults	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. Guyabano, Okra and Camote tops are available all year round.	4.90	VHP	4.60	VHP	4.63	VHP
2. The materials could be produced easily.	4.83	VHP	4.70	VHP	4.73	VHP
3. Snacks like ice cream need less effort to produce.	4.90	VHP	4.37	HP	4.57	VHP
4. The Ingredients cost less.	4.93	VHP	4.63	VHP	4.70	VHP
5. The raw materials for the product are locally available.	4.97	VHP	4.80	VHP	4.87	VHP
Overall Weighted Mean	4.91	VHP	4.62	VHP	4.70	VHP

Table 23. Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of GUOKCA Ice Cream with 120 ml Proportion of Production Cost

Indicators	Respondents					
	Teenagers		Young Adults		Adults	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. It has a competitive price.	4.93	VHP	4.60	VHP	4.73	VHP
2. It is economical.	4.93	VHP	4.60	VHP	4.83	VHP
3. It is cheaper due to the abundance of localized material.	4.97	VHP	4.60	VHP	4.80	VHP
4. Little manpower is needed in making ice cream.	4.97	VHP	4.63	VHP	4.90	VHP
5. It needs little capital to produce the product.	4.97	VHP	4.70	VHP	4.87	VHP
Overall Weighted Mean	4.95	VHP	4.63	VHP	4.83	VHP

It can be gleaned on the table that the teenagers, young adults, and adult respondents evaluated the production cost of GUOKCA Ice Cream with 120ml proportion as Very High Potential with the overall weighted means of 4.95, 4.63, and 4.83, respectively. This means that GUOKCA ice cream with 120ml proportion with respect to production cost is economical because ingredients can be bought in an affordable price due to abundance of localized materials. All groups of respondents were aware of the market availability and production cost of the ingredients.

Table 24. Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of GUOKCA Ice Cream with 120 ml Proportion of Consumer Demand

Indicators	Respondents					
	Teenagers		Young Adults		Adults	
	WM	VI	WM	VI	WM	VI
1. The product can meet the consumer demand.	5.00	VHP	4.77	VHP	4.73	VHP
2. It can satisfy the consumer because of its nutritive value.	5.00	VHP	4.70	VHP	4.80	VHP
3. It could be sold at lower price compared to other commercially prepared ice creams.	5.00	VHP	4.70	VHP	4.73	VHP
4. It could be likened by people all ages.	5.00	VHP	4.73	VHP	4.57	VHP
5. Guyabano fruit, Okra fruit and camote tops extract have health benefits.	5.00	VHP	4.93	VHP	4.77	VHP
Overall Weighted Mean	5.00	VHP	4.77	VHP	4.72	VHP

It can be observed on the table that the teenagers, young adults, and adult respondents evaluated the consumer demand of GUOKCA Ice Cream with 120ml proportion as Very High Potential with the overall weighted means of 5.00, 4.77, 4.72, respectively. This showed that GUOKCA ice cream with 120ml proportion with respect to consumer demand met evaluators satisfaction because of the nutritive benefits, it influenced their liking. Producing healthy ice cream may one factor to determine market success.

Significant Differences Among the Evaluations of Three Groups of Respondents on the Level of Marketability of GUOKCA Ice Cream with Different Proportions

It is apparent on the table that the teenagers, young adults, and adult respondents' evaluations on the marketability level of GUOKCA as ice cream ingredients with 45 mL proportion in terms of supply availability, production cost, and consumer demand do not mean significant differences with the corresponding computed F values of 2.33, 2.83, and 2.75, respectively which are smaller than the critical F value of 3.10. Hence, the respondents' evaluations are similar.

Table 25. *Summary of Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of GUOKCA Ice Cream with 45 ml Proportions*

Criteria	Computed F Value	Critical F Value	Decision	Interpretation
a. Supply Availability	2.33	3.10	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant
b. Production Cost	2.83	3.10	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant
c. Consumer Demand	2.75	3.10	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant

Table 26. *Summary of Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of GUOKCA Ice Cream with 90 ml Proportions*

Criteria	Computed F Value	Critical F Value	Decision	Interpretation
a. Supply Availability	1.87	3.10	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant
b. Production Cost	2.89	3.10	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant
c. Consumer Demand	2.91	3.10	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant

As gleaned on the table, the teenagers, young adults, and adult respondents' evaluations on the marketability level of GUOKCA as ice cream ingredients with 90 mL proportion in terms of supply availability, production cost, and consumer demand do not show significant differences with the particular computed F values of 1.87, 2.89, and 2.91, respectively which are lesser than the critical F value of 3.10. This supports that the respondents' evaluations are not different. Respondents strongly believed that cost of production does not affect supply and demand because making ice cream requires less effort and less capital to produce.

Table 27. *Summary of Analysis of Variance of Respondents' Evaluations on the Marketability Level of GUOKCA Ice Cream with 120 ml Proportions*

Criteria	Computed F Value	Critical F Value	Decision	Interpretation
a. Supply Availability	2.87	3.10	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant
b. Production Cost	2.98	3.10	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant
c. Consumer Demand	2.82	3.10	Fail to Reject the H_0	Not Significant

As shown on the table, the teenagers, young adults, and adult respondents' evaluations on the marketability level of GUOKCA as ice cream ingredients with 120 mL proportion in terms of supply availability, production cost, and consumer demand do not indicate significant differences with the respective computed F values of 2.87, 2.98, and 2.82 respectively which are below the critical F value of 3.10. This means that the respondents' evaluations are the same. The three groups of respondents perceive the marketability of the product as income and profit opportunity as demand for ice cream rises, ice cream prices rise, and producers make more of it for supply of raw materials are cheap and widely available.

Physicochemical Analysis

Table 28. *Summary of Physicochemical analysis result of GUOKCA Ice cream*

Analyte per 100g	Decision
Sugar	7.08
Vitamins C	Less than 3*
pH Level	5.01 @ 23.5°C
Moisture	68.7

Based on the results of physicochemical analysis result from the produced GUOKCA as ice cream ingredients, the ice cream contains 7.08 sugar, 68.7 moisture, and less than 3* of Vitamins C. With a pH level of 5.01 at 23.5 °C. It also implies that the research ice cream has the nutrients which is evident from the analysis.

Comments and Suggestions offered by the Three Groups of Respondents to improve the product

The comments of the three groups of respondents to the acceptability and marketability of GUOKCA ice cream are, as follows: a) The ice cream produced tastes so good and natural taste of guayabano is evident; b) Delicious and good for the health; c) 45ml and 90ml GUOKCA ice cream taste different from the others; d) The taste was good and very recommendable to market because it is healthy; e) It is a great idea to have this project, for its nutritional and beneficial value; and f) The ice cream tastes good plus it has healthy benefits unlike other ice cream.

The suggestions of the three groups of respondents to improve the marketability and acceptability of GUOKCA ice cream are, as follows: a) If the taste of 90ml and the smoothness of 120ml could be combined will be a good product; b) Ice cream product will be more delicious if it was sweeter; c) Lessen the amount of camote tops extract because it smells like tea.

Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, the conclusions derived are the following:

The prepared GUOKCA ice cream is acceptable among the three groups of respondents in terms of appearance, aroma, taste, and texture based on the results on the evaluation and level of acceptability.

The GUOKCA ice cream is a great product to introduce in the market since it has a high marketability potential in terms of product cost, supply availability and consumer demand.

The GUOKCA ice cream has healthy benefits since its ingredients contain good nutritional values.

GUOKCA ice cream when eaten makes the person enjoy the same while becoming healthy at the same time.

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